

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Guide for evaluating the assessment process

Full resource

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Introduction

Summary

Based on SCOPE Framework (INORMS 2023), evaluating your evaluation is a reflective process and the final stage of the assessment, where the effectiveness and impact of the evaluation itself are assessed. This involves reviewing whether the evaluation met its aims, was sufficiently formative and/or summative, and opportunities for improvement in future evaluations.

Since the landscape of research assessment is currently changing rapidly due to, e.g., new RRA initiatives such as CoARA, monitoring and evaluating research systems is even more important.

The aim of the present guide is to help establish the criteria for evaluating the evaluation and to identify which actors could be included (e.g., the evaluands. This guide is primarily meant for research assessment professionals in, e.g., research performing institutions and research funding organisations. The focus of the guide is on researcher assessment but it can be used in research assessment where appropriate.

This guide is a resource for evaluation of the assessment process. Purpose of the guide is reflecting on the assessment process, e.g.:

- Were the aims achieved?
- How to improve upcoming assessment and evaluation processes?
- Was the documentation transparent and open enough?
- Was the process in line with the principles of responsible assessment?

This guide gives tips and presents resources (e.g., SCOPE framework, CoARA's reform journey, recommendations by Science Europe) for defining criteria for evaluating evaluation and identifying relevant actors (stakeholders) to be included in the evaluation of evaluation. The guide focuses on the assessment *process*.

Guide as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to Open Science (OS). Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this guide supports the structured organization of evaluating the evaluation.

[SCOPE framework](#) is a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for stage E.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Why is there a need for evaluating the assessment process?

Reflection is an important part of the evaluation process. Since the landscape of research assessment is currently changing rapidly due to, e.g., new RRA initiatives such as CoARA, monitoring and evaluating research systems is even more important.

According to Hall & Hall (2004), reflection is “*thinking with a purpose or outcome, so all evaluation is a form of reflection: activities are thought about, and written about with the express purpose of deciding whether they have value or not, whether they need to be improved and how development might be devised*”.

Based on SCOPE Framework (INORMS 2023), evaluating your evaluation is a “*reflective process and the final stage of the assessment, where the effectiveness and impact of the evaluation itself are assessed.*” This involves reviewing whether the evaluation met its aims, was sufficiently formative and/or summative, and opportunities for improvement in future evaluations.

Science Europe (2020) states in their publication *Position Statement and Recommendations on Research Assessment Processes*, that “*it is essential for public research organisations to regularly consider how their assessment mechanisms cope with the requirements of a research system that continually evolves, and whether novel approaches can be used to improve them*”.

Establishing the criteria

Assessment evaluation criteria are important for measuring the effectiveness of assessments. Defining the criteria for evaluating the evaluation helps to

1. establish clear expectations
2. make sure that both the evaluators and evaluands understand the goals and standards.

Transparency increases trust. In addition, well-defined evaluation criteria can be used across different assessments, enabling for ongoing learning and development of processes. The criteria should not however be applied mechanistically, because the purpose of the evaluation affects the use of criteria. Instead, the criteria should be customized to the context of the evaluation and also according to the needs of relevant stakeholders.

Consider evaluating the assessment process on the following principles:

1. **Relevance and fitness for purpose**
 - a. Was the assessment aligned with its stated aims and objectives?
2. **Effectiveness**
 - a. Did the assessment process achieve its intended outcomes?
3. **Efficiency and proportionality**
 - a. Were the resources and methods appropriate and not overly burdensome?
4. **Transparency and openness**
 - a. Was the methodology clear, the documentation sufficient, and the results communicated openly?
5. **Fairness and inclusivity**
 - a. Were diverse perspectives and actors included in both the assessment and meta-evaluation?
6. **Consistency with responsible research assessment values**
 - a. Did the process align with relevant frameworks like **DORA (2012)** and **CoARA (2022)**?

Reflective questions to use:

- Were the **aims** of the assessment clearly stated and achieved?
- Were the **methods appropriate and proportional** to the stakes of the decision?
- Was the process sufficiently **transparent, documented, and reproducible**?
- Did the process adhere to **responsible assessment principles** (e.g., avoiding overreliance on journal metrics)?
- Were **improvements identified and implemented** for future iterations?

Explore relevant SCOPE+i Resources:

- Guide on choosing an assessment method. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525721>
- Open Science assessment guide. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525630>

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Identifying actors to be involved

The second principle of SCOPE is “**evaluate with the evaluated**”, which is important to keep in mind when evaluating the assessment process. SCOPE also highlights that “*it is important to take a broad view of who the ‘evaluated’ community is*” (INORMS 2023).

It has been recognised that the definition of the research community has historically been quite narrow, focussing only on academic researchers, rather than the broader group of technicians, librarians, and research support staff who also make a significant contribution to the research endeavour. There are also other groups that an evaluation might affect, such as **data analysts and Human Resources staff**, the inclusion of whom in the evaluation design can only improve it (INORMS 2023).

Examples of actors to involve:

- **Evaluands (researchers being assessed)**
 - as key stakeholders who can give feedback on fairness and clarity.
- **Evaluators/Panel members**
 - those applying criteria, who can reflect on feasibility and adequacy of processes.
- **Research managers and administrators**
 - with oversight on institutional policy.
- **Funders and policy-makers**
 - who shape incentives and assessment frameworks.
- **External experts or independent reviewers**
 - for impartiality in meta-evaluation.
- **Professional bodies/associations**
 - to align with broader sector standards (e.g., CoARA).

List of stakeholders and actors of the scholarly communications ecosystem by Jones & Murphy (2021):

- Policy makers
- Funders
- Institutional leadership
- Data stewards and curators
- Subject-specific and data librarians
- Open scholarship trainers
- Mainstream researcher at each career stage
- Infrastructure experts
- Technologists
- Standards organizations
- CRIS vendors

Tip: you can use the **Stakeholder mapping template** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525686> as a help to identify the potential actors.

Questions to consider:

- Were all relevant actors engaged in the process?

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- Were feedback mechanisms in place for each group?
- How will the feedback be used to improve the future assessment processes?

Useful resources

SCOPE+i Resource: Checklist for responsible assessment

Tip: You can use the whole **Checklist for responsible research assessment** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15524455> as a tool for evaluating the evaluation.

Questions to consider from the Checklist:

- Have the selected criteria, e.g., value statement, purpose statement, been consistently followed throughout the assessment process?
- Have the phases and conclusions of the assessment and their justifications been documented?
- Was the progress of the assessment process communicated to the subjects of assessment at all the relevant stages?
- Were the reasons leading to the outcome of the assessment process communicated clearly to the subjects of assessment?
- If feedback from the process was received, was it handled and used to improve the upcoming assessment processes?

SCOPE Framework: Evaluate your evaluation

The final stage of SCOPE is E, Evaluate your evaluation (INORMS 2023). After an assessment process has been concluded, it is important to check, e.g.

- Did the process reach its aims?
- Are the results useful?
- Did the evaluation approach bring new insights to what was being evaluated?
- Did the evaluation cause unintended consequences?

If for example there were unintended consequences, they should be considered when interpreting the results and addressed prior to future assessments (Himanen et al. 2024). It should also be kept in mind that the tools available to undertake an evaluation (e.g., the data sources and indicators available) as well as values, missions, and strategies, are subject to change (Himanen et al. 2024).

Questions to consider (INORMS 2023):

- What **VALUE** did you get from the evaluation?
 - Did it generate useful intelligence/outcomes in line with the values you sought to evaluate?
 - What did you anticipate that success would look like?
- In what **CONTEXTS** might you evaluate your evaluation?
 - At what level of granularity (researcher, group, department) and for what purpose (advocating for the initiative or monitoring progress).

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- What are your **OPTIONS** for evaluating your evaluation?
 - When might be a suitable time to run the evaluation? Are there existing mechanisms you can tap into, such as staff surveys, or data sources, to assess how successful the evaluation has been?
- Can you **PROBE** the evaluation outcomes to identify any unintended consequences or discriminatory effects?

Having evaluated your evaluation, you are then in a position to either redesign it or rerun it as it is (INORMS 2023).

Science Europe’s Recommendations for Evaluating and monitoring the robustness of research assessment processes

In 2019, Science Europe launched a study into the research assessment processes at research organisations. In the study “robustness” was understood as *“the capacity of selection processes to reliably and fairly assess the quality of proposals/researchers, in line with the objectives of the evaluation, and to select them for funding/career progression schemes”* (Science Europe 2020).

Based on the study

- **72%** of responding organisations have evaluated the robustness of their assessment processes, with **41% evaluating them at regular intervals**
- **28%** of surveyed organisations, however, have never evaluated their assessment processes.

According to the study, most reported evaluations focus on the scientific outcomes of assessments rather than the process itself (Science Europe 2020). Thus, the recommendations by Science Europe (2020) focus on the process and not the scientific outcomes of the assessment: *“It is important to recognise that these recommendations are primarily about assessment processes and methods, and not so much about criteria. In recent times, the appropriateness of various criteria (such as journal metrics) has been questioned through initiatives such as the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment and the Leiden Manifesto on Research Metrics. This is a highly relevant debate, where a careful separation of assessment processes and criteria needs to be made”* (Science Europe 2020).

Recommendations (please see Science Europe 2020 for more details):

- All organisations **should conduct evaluations** of the robustness of their assessment processes.
 - The use and monitoring of **key performance indicators** by assessment scheme may aid evaluations.
 - Organisations should consider also **involving applicant and reviewer feedback** in such process evaluations.
- Organisations should **re-evaluate their processes at fixed intervals**, whenever broad reforms to assessments are implemented, or when problems are identified.
- Organisations should consider the **benefits of sharing knowledge** with other organisations about the performance of their assessment processes and good practices identified to foster mutual learning.

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- Sharing **lessons learnt and good practices** between research organisations can allow for better benchmarking of results and promote faster improvement of the assessment processes of the community as a whole.

CoARA's Reform journey: a suggested process for achieving the Commitments

Also, the CoARA agreement (CoARA 2022) emphasises the importance of evaluating assessment criteria, methods, tools and processes and encourages signing institutions to learn from their own evaluations as well as from those of others. Below are the steps from the “Reform journey: a suggested process for achieving the Commitments” (CoARA 2022, Annex 3), with steps most relevant to evaluating the evaluation highlighted with bold.

“The reform journey sets out a suggested, non-prescriptive step-by-step process to help organisations achieve the Commitments. This journey is presented as chronological steps; however, the change process will probably not be chronological, and organisations can adapt the journey and start from the step they deem most appropriate for their context.”

1. Allocate resources, whether in terms of capacity or budget, to actively engage in the reform journey
2. Communicate your intention to reform, explain how you have started the process of reviewing or developing criteria, tools and processes in line with the core commitment
3. **Evaluate current assessment practices** in terms of alignment with the Principles and Commitments, consider also what currently works well and how this can be retained in parallel to any new practice - **Re-evaluate at fixed intervals**, whenever broad reforms to assessments are implemented, or when problems are identified
4. Engage those being assessed in the development and design of assessment criteria and processes, work with researchers to enable consideration of differences between disciplines and career levels
5. **Develop existing and design new assessment criteria, tools, and processes with assessors and those that are assessed**; consider the diversity of contributions including: diverse outputs beyond journal publications and in different languages; diverse practices including those that contribute to robustness, openness, transparency, and inclusiveness of research and the research process including peer review, teamwork and collaboration; and diverse activities including teaching, leadership, supervision, training, and mentoring, according to the nature of each research discipline
6. **Interrogate developed and new approaches by working with assessors and those that are assessed** (e.g. who might new approaches discriminate against; how might they be gamed; what are the potential unintended consequences)
7. Implement developed and new assessment criteria, tools, and processes according to the Principles and Commitments; consider awareness raising, rewards, policies, training, infrastructure, and capacity building and include data collection **to support monitoring, evaluation and mutual learning**
8. **Evaluate developed and new assessment criteria, tools, and processes**
9. **Share data / information, participate in mutual learning** within and beyond the Coalition, supported by mechanisms developed by the Coalition

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10. **Coordinate with other organisations** at national and international level, and promote international coordination and harmonisation
11. **Continue to evolve assessment criteria, tools, and processes based on learning from own evaluations and those of others**

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